

ISic0297

Inscribed base of a dedication to Venus Victrix

Language

Type

Material

Object

Editor

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Autopsy

2017.03.20

Last Change

2017-12-03 - Jonathan Prag cleaned epidoc

Place of origin (ancient)

Hybla

Gereatis

Place of origin (modern)

Paternò

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di
Catania, inventory 354

Physical Description

oval
A small
hexagonal base, with moulding at top and bottom. An
cavity is visible in the top surface into which the
original votive statue will have been
inserted.

Dimensions

Height 37.4 cm

Width 17.3 cm

Depth 23 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1-10: 12-29 mm

Interlineation

Line line1 to line1 : mm

Text

1. Vener

2. ri

3. Victri

4. ci ·

5. Hyblen

6. si ·
7. C (aius) Public (ius) Dona tus
10. d (ono) · d (edit)

Apparatus

Text of Prag based on autopsy

Translation (en)

(Dedicated to) Venus Victrix Hyblensis. Caius Publicius Donatus gave this as a gift.

Translation (it)

Alla Venere Vincitrice ibleense Caio Publicio Donato offrì in dono.

Commentary

This statue base is the only Latin inscription from Paternò, and is important both for its dedication to Venus Victrix (Venus Victorious) and for the reference to Hybla. This is the only dedication to Venus Victrix from Sicily, although dedications are found across the Roman Empire, especially in the northern and western provinces. The epithet 'Hyblensis', 'of Hybla' provides important evidence (but not proof) for the identification of Paternò with ancient Hybla Gereatis, although at least two cities in ancient Sicily were called Hybla. The statue was already missing when the base was found, but there is good evidence for the Venus Victrix type, principally from Roman coins from the time of Julius Caesar onwards.

Digital identifiers:

TM 491509

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